
INFLUENCE OF COVID-19 LOCKDOWN ON CRIME IN IDAH, IDAH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, Idah local government area, Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically; the study investigated the types of crime that were prevalent during covid-19 lockdown in Idah, the determinant of crime in Idah during covid-19 lockdown, the influence of covid-19 lockdown on crime rate in Idah, and the effects of such crime on residents of Idah during Covid-19 lockdown. The study relied principally on primary method of data collection using questionnaire and interview guide; the sample size for this study was 383 respondents, Routine Activity and Anomie Theory was adapted as theoretical framework for the study. The finding in this study shows that 88.9% of the total respondents agreed that burglary of commercial areas increase during the covid-19 lockdown. The study also found that 81.3% of the total respondents agreed that economic hardship/poverty were major determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown in Idah. Why 54.2% of the total respondents agreed that Covid-19 lockdown era had significantly influenced rise in crime rate. Although, 93% of the total respondents agreed that increase in poverty was the effects of crime during covid-19 lockdown. Based on these findings, the study recommends: that security personnel in Idah, need to strengthen their strategies to clamp down rates of crime occurrence during any emergency like covid-19 lockdown. There is need for Nigeria government to provide sufficient palliative with widely and fairly distribution to cushion the effect of any likely pandemic lockdown, as this will help in reducing the level at which economic hardship/ poverty resulting from lockdown could push some individual into crime.

KEYWORDS: Influence, Covid-19, Lockdown, Crime, Idah, Nigeria

Introduction

Covid-19 (Corona virus) has become a universal public health pandemic that has elicited anomie conditions, impacting daily routines due to the introduction of lockdown measure to flatten the curve of the pandemic from spreading (Miller & Blumstein, 2020). It is a serious acute respiratory condition that manifested and gave rise to Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) (Lone & Ahmed, 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) (2020) originally detected the virus and claimed that it originated from the wholesale market in Wuhan City, China, in December 2019.

However, Ezeigwe (2021) maintain that a novel corona virus was identified as the causative agent of various COVS, and was declare as pandemic on 11th day of February 2020, the researcher elucidate that WHO conditionally named this novel corona virus pneumonia as "COVID -19", based on phylogeny, taxonomy, and established practice; which made the corona virus study group to quickly sparked a global health emergency alert, as it spread to 216 countries, including Nigeria. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome corona virus [SARS-COV-2], according to the author, is the seventh member of the like (SARS-COV) and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome [MERS] and lower respiratory infection; these are corona virus family that can cause Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) in humans.

Solymosi et al. (2021) equally posited that Covid-19 is an infectious disease brought on by a recently discovered corona virus, which as of May 10th, 2021, had spread to 220 countries with over 158 million confirmed cases, 3.3 million confirmed deaths, and 136 million recovered worldwide. Correspondingly, they indicated that about 18.7 million people's lives had been influenced due to the mandatory isolations/quarantines that were mandated. However, Nigeria is not an exception to the widespread effects of Covid-19 on many nations around the world, but Africa was the last continent to experience the pandemic's effects; for instance, on February 14, 2020, Egypt reported the first case of COVID-19 on the continent, while On February 27, 2020, a patient from Italy travelling by plane reported the first case of COVID-19 in Nigeria (Lone & Ahmed, 2020).

Meanwhile, the worldwide lockdown is a rare occurrence brought on by the need to save lives from the ravaging pandemic: It was implemented in both domestic and international. Domestically, government restrict people's movement and instructed confinement to homes; on the other hand, International lockdown involves lock down of national borders, restricting the movement of citizens and goods, which hampered the economic and human relations that had previously existed among countries (Onyeaka *et al.*, 2021).

Besides, in response to the Covid-19 outbreak, governments all over the world passed laws mandating the avoidance of unnecessary contact as well as the adoption of social seclusion and lockdowns (Farell, 2020). However, Lockdown is a temporary condition imposed by government during the spread of an epidemic or disease, during which time residents must remain inside their houses and refrain from or restrict their public contact-related activities outside the home (Piryani *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, it is against the above backdrop that this study examined the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah.

Statement of the Problem

Ever since Covid-19 emerges with its anticipatory lockdown policy put in place to reduce the spread of Covid-19, different media reportage as well as research had captured different kinds of issues in connection to Covid-19 lockdown measure; meanwhile, the lockdown measure were characterize with other problems such as crime, hunger, inflation etc, despite the fact that this preventive measure were probably taken for the benefit of the public; in agreement with the above assertion, a study found that Covid-19 lockdown has become a causal mechanism for recession which triggers unemployment and poverty while the heterogeneity of the distress increased inequality, affect economic incentives of most workers of the private sectors thereby propelling some individuals into criminal activities (Schargroddsky & freira, 2021).

In affirmation to the above claim, Jahankhani *et al.* (2022) also posited that COVID-19, which also has an influence on crime, is certainly one of the most notable global pandemics in modern human history. The researcher continued, that "One unique aspect of this emergency is the government response of issuing legal stay-at-home orders to try and slow the spread of the virus; however, the government response of legally mandating people to stay at home is to lower the level of the transmission rate of the virus, but does not prevent crime from occurring." Although saving lives is the priority in the initial stages of this global pandemic, unfortunately, security was not given primary importance in this era, which created a distraction or a chance for criminals to strike and exploit the circumstance to their own financial gain.

In addition, Assessment Capacity Projects (ACAPS) (2020) maintain that the economic strain brought on by the lockdown caused people to lose their jobs, which in turn caused civil unrest, an increase in violence, as well as and protests against containment measures. This gives us a glimpse into how hoodlums and law enforcement officers clashed in some parts of this country. They explained that the loss of a source of income and the rising level of insecurity cause some poor households or individuals to turn to negative coping mechanisms like criminal activity.

Moreover, Farrell (2020), who studied how crime patterns changed during the pandemic, posited that there was an increase in the availability of suitable targets for cybercrime, online child exploitation, exposure to terrorist propaganda, and the sale of fake pandemic medical products online, including face masks, medication, and personal protective equipment (PPE). However, Hanafi and Okere (2021) in their media reportage expressed their opinion that the Kogi State government has raised an alarm that criminals are using face masks intended to stop the spread of COVID-19 to conceal their identities and rob in public places, and that they took time to survey their target before engaging in their criminal activities.

Whereas, Bello and Olalekan (2021) found that criminals had been using the period of lockdown as an opportunity to devise new ways to engage in various criminal activities, including rape, banditry, cybercrime, as well as the sale of fake medical products online, false information, and the creation of fake friendships for an exploitative purpose. In view of the aforementioned findings, lockdown imposed by various government of the world to curtail the spread of Covid-19 had compelled many people to stay in door and work from home, with many others spending time online which could serve as a mechanism for increment or reduction in crime rate as Covid-19's secondary effects. However, this made the researcher to become fascinating in conducting a study in this topic, the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, since research as regards to the aforementioned topic is yet to be conducted

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions;

- i. What types of crime were prevalent during the COVID-19 lockdown in Idah?
- ii. What are the determinants of crime during the COVID-19 lockdown in Idah?
- iii. To what extent does the COVID-19 lockdown influence crime rate in Idah?
- iv. What are the effects of crime on residents of the Idah during Covid-19 lockdown?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The purpose or aim this study is to analyze the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, Idah local government area, Kogi state, Nigeria. However, the specific objectives includes, to:

- i identify the types of crime that were prevalent during the COVID-19 lockdown in Idah
- ii. investigate the determinants of crime during the COVID-19 lockdown in Idah.
- iii examine the extent of influence of the COVID-19 lockdown on crime rate in the Idah.
- iv. identify the effects of crime on residents of Idah during the COVID-19 lockdowns.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are to guide this research:

H₁: Covid-19 lockdown will not significantly influence the types of crime prevalent in Idah.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between the determinants of crimes with influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime.

H₃: Covid-19 lockdown has no significant relationship with crime rate in Idah.

H₄: Covid-19 lockdown has no significant effect of crime on residents of Idah.

Significance of the Study

The results of this study will give people access to actual data that will serve as the baseline survey for further studies on the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime. The study's conclusions will be helpful to the government, criminology students, and policy makers by giving them empirical facts that can be used in the design of public policies to reduce the prevalence of crime during any anticipated pandemic lockdown. The research will also broaden our understanding of COVID-19, lockdown, and criminality. The study will provide details on how the COVID-19 lockdown will affect crime and suggested ways to take preventative action to detect and control crime during any future pandemic lockdown. The study will significantly enhance already published works and give direction for new research.

The Scope of the Study

The study focused on how the COVID-19 lockdown influenced crime in Idah. The male and female residents of the Idah, who are 16years of age and above, make up the study's gender scope. Idah, in Idah Local Government Area, Kogi state, Nigeria, is the study's geographical focus. However, the researcher's belief that Idah is a good representative where the influence of COVID-19 lockdown on crime can easily be identified, Idah is made up of ten political wards. These ten political wards are Ega, Ede, Ichala, Igala-ogba, Igecheba, Ogegele, Owoli- Apa, Sabogari and Ukwaja and Ugwoda, ward. Nevertheless, the following areas were covered as part of the content scope of this study: the types of crime that were prevalent during Covid-19 lockdown; the determinants of crime during Covid-19 lockdown; the; Influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime rate in the; and the effect of crime on residents during Covid-19 lockdown. The study was conducted between December 2022 - March 2023.

Literature Review

The review of relevant and related literature to provide the needed conceptual background to the study was done as follows:

Conceptual Review

Under this section, some concepts used in this work are explained to portray clear picture of the issue under discussion;

Covid-19

COVID-19 is a contagious airborne illness that is typically contracted by contact with an infected individual since it is spread through droplets from their mouth or nose (WHO, 2020). Ushoh et al. (2021) claim that the Novel Corona virus 2019, commonly referred to as Covid-19, is the most recent pathogen variant, also known as "severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus-2, SARS Cov-2. Corona virus is a family of viruses that can cause respiratory sickness in people. They further explain that the word "corona" is derives from the virus's multiple spikes that resemble crowns; severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), middle east respiratory syndrome (MERS), and the common cold are all diseases brought on by corona viruses. The COVID-19 virus causes one or more of the following symptoms, including fever, chills, cough, shortness of breath, fatigue, headaches, new loss of taste or smell, sore throat, runny nose, vomiting, and diarrhea. The aforementioned makes COVID-19 a novel viral infection that can spread quickly through the air, causing symptoms such as difficulty breathing, a cold, fever, cough, runny nose, and sneezing; if not carefully managed by a qualified health professional, it could be fatal. According to Binsaleh *et al.* (2022), the [WHO] declared a Public Health Emergency of International Concern in January 2020 and a pandemic in March 2020 as

a result of the virus' quick spread. They added that acute respiratory distress syndrome is frequently associated to pathological manifestations of the disease in the infected population, which they also defined as having symptoms that range from mild to severe.

Lockdown

A restriction policy or emergency protocol, as defined by Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia (2020), requires individuals or a group of people to remain in one place, typically because their unrestricted movement and interaction pose a threat to themselves or others. For instance, jail officials use it to restrict convicts' freedom of movement. To protect themselves from external threats, businesses lock down their buildings and computer systems. Such safeguards are put in place by governments during times of war, terrorism threats, and pandemics. Lockdowns could be classified as either preventive or emergency.

Crime

Criminologists' definitions of crime range greatly along a continuum: The highly legalistic definition of crime by Paul Tappan (1947:100, cited in Brown *et al.*, 2010:12; Ugwuoke, 2015; Isiaka & Okaphor 2018; Gomment 2019) serves as an example of this definitional continuum. It defines crime as an intentional act that violates the criminal law (statutory and case law), is committed without justification, and is punished by the state as a felony or misdemeanour. He continued by saying that there can be no assumption made when examining the offender that: People are not criminals unless they are found to have committed a crime beyond a reasonable doubt.

It is crucial to define crime from the perspectives of two separate civilizations, the Latin and Arabic civilizations, according to Ugwuoke (2015) in Gomment (2020:8). The word "crimen," which translates to "fault" or "accusation," is the term in Latin. Looking at it from an Arabic perspective, the name is derived from the word "Jarima," which is a form of the verb "jaram," which literally means "to cut" and "to earn" what is undesirable.

Types of Crime Prevalent during Covid-19 Lockdown

According to Ekpenyong *et al.* (2020), crime such as armed robbery, cybercrime, and burglary, abuse of human rights, domestic violence, gender-based violence, and bribery, are at varying rates Covid-19 lockdown. Obiako *et al.* (2021) also pointed out that during the first two weeks of the lockdown, there were several reports of arrests in Nigeria, with at least 200 persons being detained on suspicion of robbery and the rape of young girls.

Olofinbiyi *et al.* (2020) also stated that the Covid-19 lockdown has a significant influence cybercrime. Scholars claimed that as Covid-19 emerges, people begin to share the available cyberspace with unidentified cyber criminals. They also state that cybercriminals have been greatly utilizing the Covid-19 lockdown to create newly registered domains in order to draw attention from the public. It was further said that other complaints linked the purchase of face masks to two scammers from Nigeria who operated as fake internet merchants. One victim paid EUR15, 000 for the ostensibly fictitious face masks, which were never delivered. They claim that scammers have been utilizing the World Health Organization (WHO) and the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) brand names (CDCP).

More so, Ogbonnaya (2020) also stated that reports of a rise in cybercrime such as phishing attacks, malicious spam, and ransom ware in Nigeria had been made by cyber criminals who used the corona virus as bait to impersonate well-known firms and deceive customers and employees in furtherance, the researcher affirmed that made an assumption that due to the rise in cybercrime in the era of covid-19 lockdown, the nation's 2015 cybercrime law might not be sufficient to lessen the susceptibility of financial institutions, particularly the banking sector, to these offences. However, Asimi (2020) also pointed out that internet sales of bogus goods have been used to commit cybercrime.

Meanwhile, Asadu (2021) also stated that Nigeria has been rated 16th among the countries mostly affected by online crime in the globe. The scholar confirmed that the US Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) in its newest online crime report indicated "Nigeria received 443 complaints in the year 2020". He confirmed that the country was last listed in yearly reports in 2015, where it was placed third, and in 2016, where it was ranked fourth (19th).

According to Bello *et al.* (2021), statistics showed that as of May 15, 2020, 975 people had been massacred; the number of killings for April and May confirms the rise in homicide during the Covid-19 lockdown in Nigeria. In January, statistics showed that approximately 320 people had been killed; in February, 597; in March, 754; and in April, 825. Agbese (2020) offers evidence that the continued kidnapping, banditry, and killings that have increased in Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, and Niger state were caused by inadequate security measures. Although, kidnapping, in particular, is a crime that has become increasingly common in Nigeria before Covid-19 lockdown, but the era of covid-19 lockdown, only thing that has been noticed is a change in strategy, a decrease in the ransom, and a decrease in the number of victims. While the Covid-19 and neighbourhood lockout make it difficult for many families to pay huge ransoms due to the Covid-19 and community lockdown's effects on their socioeconomic status Bello *et al.* (2021).

Determinants of Crime during Covid-19 Lockdown

Economic and social variables the basis or key issues rooted in crime statistics during the Covid-19 lockdown in Nigeria. For instance, the increase in unemployment and poverty rate in Nigeria brought on by the lockdown measures to limit the pandemic could be a causal mechanism for crime during the Covid19 lockdown, according to Lone and Ahmed (2020). This is in consonance with the study conducted by Asimi (2020) which reveals that numerous individuals were discovered to be experiencing unimaginable hardship as a result of the lockdown. This is due to the fact that a greater proportion of Nigerians were living on daily wages and that the lockdown undoubtedly affected their chances of receiving their daily income, which led some individuals to turn to negative coping mechanisms like substance abuse.

In agreement with the aforementioned claim, Obiako *et al.* (2021) discovered that the initial increase in crime lockdown states was brought on by the difficulties of the lockdown and the release of prisoners from prisons throughout Nigeria. In addition, Accord (2020) claims that the poverty, unemployment, and inequality that exist across Africa, combined with the actual or perceived scarcity of basic necessities, as well as the disruptions of daily life brought on by the Covid19 lockdown to contain the virus, could lead to an increase in crime rates.

In a study conducted by Akanmu *et al.* (2021) COVID-19 pandemic and insecurity, it was discovered that poverty, weak governance, and idleness were the main drivers of the increase in crime during the Covid19 lockdown. Meanwhile, Obahopo *et al.* (2020) in their media coverage affirmed that hoodlums were aggressively questing for Covid-19 palliative leading to clashed with security personnel; the hooligans however, plundered and invaded into the private warehouses, taking fertilizer and rice in Lokoja, state Kogi capital. Although, four people were shot dead during the altercation, while 30 others, including a journalist, suffered varying degrees of injuries. Similar events occurred in Calabar, Cross River State, when a battle between hoodlums and security personnel from early on Saturday till late on Sunday night resulted in the deaths of not less than 10 people, including a pregnant mother. In addition to those murdered in the Calabar conflict, the state police command reports that at least 80 looters have been detained. Additionally, two women lost their lives on Monday in a violent incident for COVID-19 palliatives that had been stolen from a warehouse on Secretariat Road in the Gwagwalada Area Council of Abuja by thugs.

Ogbonnaya (2020) also posited that, government measures to work from in-office to online modification in order to control the spread of Covid-19 propel cyber attackers using Covid-19 as a lure to deceive people and imitate well-known brands to mislead people. According to Abdullahi *et al.* (2021), COVID19 lockdown caused the economy to collapse, businesses to shut down, and travel restrictions, all of which made it harder to get food and increased social tensions and

strain on families, which in turn led to domestic violence. The researchers buttressed that lack of parental oversight and stagnant education for children contributed to peer pressure, poor social skills, drug misuse, and online deviance. In addition, increase in such crime like armed robbery, kidnapping, extrajudicial killings was propelled by lack of governmental intervention (Amara, *et al.*, 2020). More so, frustration and lack of satisfaction arising from the social reality created by covid-19 lockdown and social distancing have led to rise in unusual and antisocial behaviours in the society (Arisukwu, 2021).

The Influence of Covid-19 Lockdown on Crime Rate

The COVID-19 lockdown has had a significant influence on crime rate globally. For example, a research by Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime [GIATOC] (2020) found that the lockdown has had an influence on crime and illicit markets including organize crime, terrorism, street crime, internet crime, human and wildlife trafficking, enslavement, robberies and burglaries; and that the pandemic lockdown has reduced some organized crime operations while simultaneously creating opportunities for new ones. This claim was supported by evidence that there were already emerging drug gangs that were taking advantage of the confusion and uncertainty created by the rise in demand for illegal goods and services. Some of these organisations infiltrated health systems and used life-saving resources for their own criminal gain, which made the government's response to the problem less effective.

Moreover, in most nations with stronger lockdown policies, robberies, thefts, and burglaries decreased dramatically, falling by more than 50%, according to [UNODC] (2020). It is likely that this decline was caused by a decrease in both the number of crimes committed and the number of crimes reported. They support that by noting that in other nations, homicide had a temporary reduction of 25% or more. In other cases, there were either no obvious changes or the variation in the number of homicide victims which remained within its pre-pandemic range. Any notable changes, however, were transient, and pre-pandemic dynamics soon returned. World Wildlife Report (2020) which observes that falsified medicines in the wake of COVID-19 is an emerging threat for security and public health in Nigeria. As an intervention, UNODC continues its support to Nigerian Correctional Service with protective kits for COVID-19 prevention in custodial centers in Nigeria.

According to Tade (2020), one of the unintended and emerging effects of lock-down, intended to stop the Corona virus from spreading in the majority of African nations, is violent criminality, including murder, kidnapping, domestic violence (gender-based violence), and growing cyber-crime among other criminal activities. This is consistent with the conclusions of the [GIATOC] (2020), which predict that as people in lockdown pass the time online; cyber scams, fraud, misinformation, and other crimes allowed by the internet expand in popularity.

Over twenty people have been killed by the police in Nigeria, and there have been claims of human rights violations while lockdowns have been enforced. Okoklie Osemene (2021) claims that during lockdown in Lagos, Warri, Aba, Umuahia, and other places; there was store looting, robbery, and killings by security forces. While crime rates were noticeably lower than they were prior to COVID-19, the lockdown did not stop troublemakers from committing violent crimes such armed robberies, banditry attacks, police assault, and kidnapping. Additionally, the State is charged with using the pandemic to commit "palliative fraud" and "COVID-19 fund fraud" (Tade, 2020).

In another development, [ACAPS] (2020) found these trending during the lockdown in Nigeria:

Between 30th March and mid-April, following the beginning of lockdowns, the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) recorded extrajudicial killings and abuse of power by the Nigerian security forces. Some people were killed by law enforcement agents for allegedly not complying with containment measures. In the same period, the NHRC recorded 33 incidents of inhuman and degrading treatment, as well as 27 incidents of unlawful arrest and detention recorded in

areas under lockdown or movement restrictions, as well as intimidation and arrest of journalists.

The Covid-19 lockdown in Nigeria has a substantial influence on interpersonal violence since it makes it less likely that crimes like theft, robbery, shoplifting, and physical assault outside of the home will be perpetrated. In the long run, however, business closures and the subsequent unemployment and loss of income may have an influence on crime, particularly acquisitive and profit-oriented crime, where social and economic safety nets are insufficient to ensure livelihoods, leading to looting and rioting where the populace is negatively affected economically and dissatisfied with the government's response to their needs.

In other words, according to Sunday (2020), a security expert, there were signs that there would be a rise in criminal activity during and after the Covid19 lockdown, and that "criminals will take advantage of the lack of law enforcement resources to perpetrate property and violent crime in commercial corridors," following the crippling of businesses by the lockdown over the outbreak of corona virus. He claimed that Dennis Amachre, the former head of the DSS, had predicted that since everyone was at home, criminals would avoid residential areas. However, he cautioned that domestic violence crimes should not be overlooked. In other words, Amara (2020) also posited, that Covid-19 pandemic lockdown had wreak untold disorder on the fragile state of Nigeria; which thereby triggered a lot of social unrest and conflict in a country as well as increase in crime rates and insecurity.

However, Usman (2020) also maintained that the crime rate had also significantly decreased following the lockdown due to Covid-19; pickpockets are ineffective in the vast of Lagos since their victims are compelled to stay inside. More so, the constant attacks by motorcycle-riding thieves are also relieving the workers and traders who often left their homes before 5am. The researcher confirmed that due to the lockdown in Lagos, traffic thieves, Catch-in-the-Air gangs, and thieves who target bank customers also have their fair share of regrets after the forced break-in operation.

Effect of Crime during Covid-19 Lockdown

Crime during covid-19 lockdown has an economic cost effects, for instance, UN (2020) report on gender base violence affirmed that GBV has an economic cost to Nigeria in terms of prevention, responses, and opportunity cost, these cost include health, justice, and other services; which are borne out by the victims, household, community, government as well as civil organization. According to a study conducted by Akanmu *et al* (2021), the main consequences of crime experienced during the COVID19 lockdown in Nigeria were fear (phobia) and a loss in socioeconomic capacity. In tandem with the above assertion, Amara *et al* (2020) also posited that crime during covid-19 lockdown become synonymous with national security, especially when citizen of a country live in fear of their lives and properties. More so, outrageous corruptions perpetrated by security personnel during the Covid-19 lockdown in Nigeria have been undermined the efforts of the Presidential Task Force on COVID19 in Nigeria. For example, the failure of the security forces to prohibit the vehicle movement from one state to another in exchange of cash for free passage provides an opportunity for inter-state transmission of COVID-19 (Osemene 2021). The precarious state of instability and crime in Nigeria, according to Bello *et al*, (2021), hinders the degree of reactions to the struggle against Covid-19. Olaiya (2020) documents a rise in murders and a shoddy security response in Nigeria during the COVID19 lockdown.

Empirical Review

In the study conducted by Uzobo and Ayinmoro (2021) also found the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), shows that 9% have experienced sexual violence; with the lockdown across the 36 states and Federal Capital Territory occasioned by the outbreak of the corona virus, this figure rise drastically. The researchers affirmed that domestic violence reports from Nigeria have indicated that rape and sexual violence increased during the months of the lockdown in most states. The researchers buttress that a survey conducted by Partners West Africa Nigeria (PWAN) in three northern states of Nigeria (FCT, Borno and Kano states) revealed that there has been an increase in

the rate of reported cases of Sexual and Gender-Based Violence (SGBV); for instance, in Lagos, the Domestic and Sexual Violence Response Team (DSVRT) the daily reported cases of domestic and sexual abuse increased by almost 50% from the start of the Corona virus lockdown compared to just approximately 8 cases of domestic abuse previously reported before the lockdown.

In a study conducted by Akanmu *et al* (2021) on COVID-19 pandemic and insecurity: the furiousness in Nigerian communities, it was found that the occurrence of crime incidences was more prominent in areas where there was total lockdown (41.4%) and partial lockdown (35.5%) than in areas with curfew (10.4%) and only interstate travel restrictions (12.7%). The observed higher percentage in respect to total and partial restrictive measures is relative to curfew and interstate travel restriction across all crime cases. The scholar affirmed that a spike in crime like theft and rape during Covid-19 lockdown was attributed to analytical agent such as idleness, poor governance, and poverty.

Ogunlana *et al.* (2021) discovered that a total of 48 rape cases were examined, of which 12.5% resulted in femicide, in their study Pattern of rape and femicide during COVID- 19 lockdown: content and discourse analysis of digital media reports in Nigeria. The age range of the rape victims ranged from 11 to 20 years old, and 97% of them were women. Although, about 429% of the rapists were male and all between the ages of 31 and 45. Rape rates slowly rose from 5.1% in March to a peak of 33.3% in June before abruptly falling to 5.1% by the end of August 2020, with rape rates in northern Nigeria being higher. In study conducted by Abdullahi *et al.* (2021) on covid-19 and pandemic street crime, it was revealed that shutting down of economy have been responsible for high crime rate during covid-19 lockdown.

Gap in Literature

Different studies on Covid-19 lockdown and crime has been extensively documented in the literature, but the precise influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, Idah local government area, Kogi state, Nigeria have not been substantiated or addressed. Given that the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime is an academic phenomenon that has the potential to explain whether there was an increase or decrease in crime rate during Covid-19 lockdown in Idah, the determinants of crime as well as the types of crime that are prevalent and the effect of such crime on residents of Idah, this gap in the literature becomes pertinent and essential. As a result, this study will fill the vacuum in the body of research relevant to the topic.

Theoretical Framework

Routine Activity Theory

Lawrence Cohen and Marcus Felson provided a series of publications that served as the foundation for routine activity theory (1979). Instead of a transient displacement, the idea explains why crime occurs in some specific circumstances (Felson & Clarke 1998: in Argun & Daglar 2016:1188). It was cited as a reason for historical variations in crime trends. According to Cohen and Felson (1979) the prevalence and volume of violent crimes against people and crimes in which a person directly attempts to take an object are closely correlated with the interaction of three factors that represent the American way of life: lack of capable guardians, such as police, property owners, neighbours, friends, and family members, whose presence can deter crime; The presence of motivated offenders, such as the significant numbers of unemployed adults and youths that make up the addicted population and are most likely to commit crimes if they converge in a specific neighbourhood, makes a neighbourhood more likely to experience crime. Base on this, Felson (1998) in his is recent work, place less emphasis on the significance of formal guardians such as the police; he conclude that crime become a private phenomenon largely unaffected by state intervention. He now emphasizes the natural crime prevention and deterrence that occurs in the informal control system, that is the ‘ quiet and natural method by which people prevent crime in the course of daily life’ such as ordinary people, friends, family, or even strangers are the most likely capable guardians during a catastrophic era or disaster. Beside, covid-19 lockdown era is not an exception of the aforementioned claims.

The theory made the postulation that crime can be understood in terms of risk exposure; that crime is most likely to occur when a likely potential offender congregates on space and time with appropriate criminal targets in the absence of effective guidance against crime; and that when a criminal is placed close to a target firm, such business ventures become good targets for crime since their owners and customers are unavailable.

Routine activities theory has to gain empirical support in the area of exposure of victims to the offenders, with several strengths which include: routine activity theory offers a straightforward and insightful understanding of the root causes of criminal issues. In this aspect, criminals will prey on desirable targets in the absence of effective control. This emphasizes that the chemistry of crime can be reduced to the interaction of three crucial elements: a likely offender, the suitable target, and the absence of a capable guardian against crime; how these three elements are made to overlap in time-space are functions of our social arrangements and daily routines. Another important contribution is that illegal activities must feed upon other activities. Hot-spot policing, or the use of proactive policing to minimize crime, is where this chemistry is mostly measured.

The hallmark of this idea is that it places a focus on the offender before shifting to the target and guardian. The choice of a target rather than a victim highlights the physical element of the crime and might be any person or piece of property that the perpetrator wishes to gain control of. Routine Activity Theory was criticized for having the erroneous premise that criminals make rational decisions, it is possible that their reasoning differs from that of the person putting the security measure in place. The theories were also criticized on the grounds that those who, as assumed, would deter crime from occurring like homeowners, gatekeepers, receptionists, and security guards cannot be present everywhere. It was also noted that a particular place can be favourable for crime occasionally but unfavourable always or sometimes. Another criticism of the notion of routine activities is that it does not explain why motivated criminals and suitable targets congregate in the absence of capable guardians. These are referred to as criminal opportunities.

The theory of routine activities has been linked to structural change in a society and criminal activity. For instance, the lockdown strategy used to stop the spread of Covid-19 had business owners and clients removed from their establishments, making the place of business extremely vulnerable to trespassers and burglars. More so, the corona virus pandemic lockdown has altered people's behaviours in a variety of ways. Less people on the street meant fewer targets for street robberies and purse snatching, but also fewer guardians. However, the social distancing recommendation to keep 6 feet between people may have made pick-pocketing virtually difficult. The success of the attack or sexual violence of rape during Covid-19 lockdown is further enhanced by the rapist's mastery of the predator's normal behaviours and sufficient awareness of when their attractive targets would be unguarded and more vulnerable for their sexual predation. Consequently, the virus lockdown leads to an increase in certain sorts of crime, like commercial burglary brought on by absenteeism influencing lack of guardianship. Whereas hindering others, such as residential burglary because of house presence and guardianship; while home presence and lockdown can lead to domestic and violent criminality.

Research Design

A descriptive survey research design was used for the investigation. This option entails the gathering of information from a sample in order to determine influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, Kogi State, using questionnaire and Interview guide.

Study Setting

Idah is located in Kogi state Nigeria, on the eastern bank of the river Niger in the middle belt region of Nigeria. It is the headquarters of the Igala kingdom and also the Local Government Area with an area of 36kms. Idah had a population of 79755 as of the 2006 National Population census. Why it was projected at 107,500 in 2022 by the national population commission. Idah is an important fishing port

and market trading town in Nigeria with an outpost of Navy ship luard. Idah has commercial route on the river Niger, linking lokoja to the north of the country, and Onitsha in Anambra state to the south, Agenebode in Edo state across the Niger to the west. It population is primarily Igala. It comprises of ten political wards and three districts: thus, Ega district, Idah district, and Ichala district, which comprises ten political wards; Ega, Ede, Ichala, Igalaogba, Igecheba, Owoli- Apa, Ogegele, Sabogari, Ugwoda and Ukwaja ward. Idah host several federal and state establishments; among which are: Federal polytechnic, National Open University, National Population commission, Nigeria Postal Service, Nigerian Television Authority, National Inland Waterway, Nigerian Police, Nigerian Correctional Institution, Nigerian Immigration Service, as well as College of Health Science and Technology.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprise of adult male and female residents of Idah. In other words, according to Ogili (1999), the population of the study is a group of persons or aggregate items, things the researcher is interested in getting information from for the study. However, Babbie (2005) cited in Adesola (2021:105) "the population for a study is that group, usually people about whom we want to draw conclusions" The total population of Idah is 79755 as of the 2006 national population census, although, it was projected at 107,500 in 2022 by National Population Commission [NPC] Brinkhoff (2022). However, 107,500 projected figures were used as the population of the study

Sample Size

The sample size for this study comprises of 383 adult male and female residents within the Idah in Kogi State. The sample size was drawn from the projected 107500 population of the Idah local government area; in 2022. The sample size was drawn from the entire population of the study which is 107,500 using Krejcie and Morgan table (1970), as well as the formula for calculating sample size, as the determinants for sample size.

The formula for the determinant of sample size

$$S = \frac{X^2 NP (1-P)}{D^2 (N-1) + X^2 P (1-P)}$$

S= required sample size

X² the table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.841)

N= the population size s

P= the population proportion assumed to be since this would provide the maximum sample size

d= the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (.05)

Substituting the value X²=3.841, N=107700 P= 0.05, D=.05

$$S = 3.841$$

$$\frac{1 \times 107500 \times 0.5(1-0.5)}{0.05 \times (107500-1) + 3.841 \times 0.25}$$

$$\frac{3.841 \times 53750 \times 0.5}{0.0025 \times 107500 + 3.841 \times 0.25}$$

$\frac{103,226.875}{269.71025}$

=382.7 =383 approximately

However, the sample size for this study was 383 in line with the table above considering the infinite population.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria comprise male and female residents who were present in Idah during the era of covid-19 lockdown, and must be within 16years of age and above; while the criteria for exclusion, are males and females were less than 16 years of age, and those who were not in Idah during the era of covid-19 lockdown, and those who are not residents of Idah; as well as those who were sick and are under medical admission during the period of this survey.

Sampling Techniques

A cluster sampling technique was used in this research work. The sample size is made up of 383 respondents of the Idah drawn from 107500 projected population of the Idah local government area; however, to determine the number of questionnaires to be distributed; Ega ward was allocated 41 questionnaire, while remaining nine (9) political wards in Idah were allocated 38 questionnaire each; although, the allocation of the questionnaire to these ten (10) wards within Idah local government were based on clustered sampling techniques.

Source of Data Collection

The research methods used for data collection are primary and secondary sources of data collection. Although primary data and secondary information was adopted due to some constraints in getting sufficient data from the primary source, in order to get a comprehensive record of crime during Covid-19 lockdown in Idah, for accurate information and correct findings that will enable us to proffer effective suggestion to the findings.

Types of Data

This study makes use of both qualitative and quantitative data. This entails that questionnaire and interview guide were used to elicit information needed for this study. Meanwhile, quantitative data obtained were interpreted statistically to determine the influence covid-19 lockdown on crime in the study location, why qualitative data were interpreted in words.

Instrument for Data Collections

According to Ojo 2003 & Oyelekan 2019 in Owoyemi (2021), research instruments are methods or tools used for data gathering in social research; this includes questionnaire, interview guides, Focus Group discussions, and observational methods among others. However, questionnaire was as adopted as the primary data collection instrument. It was self-designed in closed ended style in format of three point likert scales consisting of Agree, Neutral and Disagree, this is in tandem with Matell and Jacoby 1971 suggestion that three point likert scales are sufficient to meet criteria of test retest reliability, concurrent validity, and predictive validity. They buttress that reliability is independent of number of responses option. In consonance wit aforementioned claims, Peterson (1985) also affirmed that, we have some cause to echo Jacoby and Matell 1971 assertion and Benson 1971, who supported that practical convenience makes three point likert scales good enough.

Reliability and Validity of Research Instrument

Pilot study was carried out in order to obtain the psychometric properties of the instrument. The pilot study was conducted among the population of the study who did not participate in main study. Twenty copies of questionnaires were distributed for participants to provide answers from which validity and reliability were obtained before the main research survey.

The study also established the degree to which instrument or scale is consistent in its result overtime. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted. In this study 35 participants (different from the participants of the main study) were recruited to complete questionnaire that hitherto has been vetted by three lecturers and expert in the fields of study. Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was used in estimating the reliability. According to Nunnally (1978) the major way to tests internal consistency reliability is Cronbach's alpha. A general accepted rule is that α of 0.6-0.7 indicates an acceptable level of reliability, and 0.8 or greater indicates a very good level (Hulin et al. 2001; Wim *et al.*, 2008). Cronbach Alpha Coefficient is chosen as it gives a numerical coefficient of the internal consistency of the variables under study.

Method of Data Analysis

The study was guided by a complete and returned questionnaire. The information provided in the questionnaire was coded, while the descriptive method of data analysis such as percentages, frequency and inferential statistic count were used to analyze the data. Meanwhile, multiple regression analysis as the statistical method was used to test the hypothesis formulated with the aid of statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0, while secondary information obtained will be summarized based on content analysis.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher was conscious of ethical guidelines and issues throughout the study, especially, during data collection, analysis, and the dissemination of research results. To implement this, the researcher first gets the approval of the supervisor; the study seeks the consent of the participant in the course of administering the questionnaire. Confidentiality of respondents' identities and responses was equally guaranteed. More so the study was not involve any attack or harm to the respondents. Meanwhile, the researcher maintains the following ethical standard for the human subject involved in carrying out research: to ensure voluntary participation of the respondents as well as to ensure the voluntary withdrawal of the respondents from participating.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Three Hundred and Eighty-Three (383) copies of questionnaire were distributed to some selected persons living in Idah, Idah Local Government Area, Kogi State. Only three hundred and sixty-nine (369) of the copies of questionnaire were correctly filled and returned. However, the analysis for the study was based on the three hundred and sixty-nine (369) copies of the questionnaire that were properly completed and returned. Tables were used to present the data generated through the questionnaire instrument.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Category	Frequency N=369	Percentage (100)
Age		
16-20 years	75	20.33
21-25 years	62	16.80
26-30 years	57	15.45
31-35 years	53	14.36
36-40 years	48	13
41-45 years	28	7.59
46-50 years	15	4.06
51-55 years	16	4.34
56 above	15	4.07
Gender		
Male	212	57.45
Female	157	42.55
Marital Status		
Single	112	30.35
Married	203	55.01
Divorce	23	6.23
Widow	19	5.15
Widower	12	3.25
Educational Attainment		
No Formal Education	-	-
Primary Education	51	13.82
Secondary Education	195	52.85
Tertiary Education	123	33.33
Ethnic Group		
Igala	255	69.11
Yoruba/Okun	30	8.13
Egbira	15	4.07
Hausa	35	9.49
Igbo	30	8.13
Others	4	1.08
Religious Belief		
Christianity	156	42.28
Islamic	200	54.20
African Traditional Religion	13	3.52
Occupation		
Civil Servant	68	18.43
Student	76	20.16
Trading	83	22.49
Farming	89	24.12
Transporter	12	3.25
Artisan	29	7.86
Retire civil servant	12	3.25
Location Base on Ward		
Ega	41	11.11
Ede	38	10.30
Igalaogba	38	10.30
Ichala	38	10.30

Igecheba	38	10.30
Ogegele	38	10.30
Owoli-Apa	38	10.30
Sabon-gari	38	10.30
Ugwoda	38	10.30
Ukwaja	38	10.30

Sources: Field Survey (2023)

Table 1: present the result of demographic profile of the respondent which shows that 20.33% were between 16-20years, 16.80% were 21-25years, 15.45% were 26-30 years, 14.36% were 31-35years of age, 13% were 36-40years, 7.59% were 41-45years, 4.06% were 46-50 years, 4.34% were 51-55year while 4.07% were 56-60 years and above. This shows that majority of the respondents fall with the age bracket of 16-20years of age. Furthermore, 57.45% of the total respondents were male while 42.55% were female. This shows that lagers populations of the respondents were male. The table further revealed that 30.35% of the respondents were single, 55.01% were married, 6.23% were divorce, 5.1.5% were widow while 3.25% were widower. The table further shows that 13.82% of the total respondents had primary education, 52.85% had secondary education while 33.33% had tertiary education. This shows that majority of the total respondents had secondary education. The table further shows that 69.11% of the respondents were Igala, 8.13% were Yoruba/Okun, 4.07% were Egbira, 9.49% were Hausa, 8.13% were Igbo while 1.08% were other tribes. This shows that majority of the total respondents were Igalas'. The table further shows the religious belief of the total respondents. The table shows the location base on the ward of the respondents. 11.11% of the total respondents were from Ega Ward, 10.30% were from Ede waed, 10.30% were from Igalao gba Ward, 10.30% were from Ichala Ward, 10.30% were from Igecheba Ward, 10.30% of the total respondents were from Ogegele Ward, 10.30% were from Owoli-Apa Ward, 10.30% were from Sabon-gari ward, 10.30% were from Ugwoda Ward while 10.30% were from Ukwaja Ward.

Table 2: Types of Crime that was Prevalent during Covid-19 Lockdown in Idah.

S/N	ITEMS	DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	AGREE	N=369	(%)
1	Opportunity for property crime increase	84 (22.8)	7 (1.9)	278 (75.3)	369	(100)
2	Burglary of commercial areas.	37 (10.0)	4 (1.1)	328 (88.9)	369	(100)
3	Burglary of residential areas.	313 (84.8)	13 (3.5)	43 (11.7)	369	(100)
4	Kidnapping.	295 (79.9)	19 (5.1)	55 (14.9)	369	(100)
5	Advance free fraud, using Covid-19 palliative as bait.	116 (31.4)	15 (4.1)	238 (64.5)	369	(100)
6	Cyber crime	148 (40.1)	53 (14.4)	168 (45.5)	369	(100)
7	Pick pocketing and purse snatching.	287 (77.8)	15 (4.1)	67 (18.2)	369	(100)
8	Domestic violence, such as assault within the family.	134 (36.3)	19 (5.1)	216 (58.5)	369	(100)

9	Assault outside domestic spheres.	300 (81.3)	17 (4.6)	52 (14.1)	369 (100)
10	Murder resulting from cultist violent.	345 (93.5)	6 (1.6)	18 (4.9)	369 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The distribution from the sample in table 2 shows that 22.8% of the total respondents disagreed that opportunity for property crime was common during -19 lockdown, 1.9% of the total respondents are Neutral while 75.3% of the total respondents agreed that opportunity for property crime increases during covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that opportunity for property crime was common during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 2 also indicates that 10% of the total respondents disagreed that burglary of commercial areas was prevalent during covid-19 lockdown, 1.1% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 88.9% of the total respondents agreed that burglary of commercial areas was common during the covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that burglary of commercial areas was prevalent during the covid-19 lockdown.

Table 2 further revealed that 84.8% of the total respondents disagreed that burglary of residential areas was prevalent during covid-19 lockdown, 3.5% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 11.7% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that residential areas was common during the pandemic lockdown.

Table 2 also shows that 79.9% of the total respondents disagreed that kidnapping skyrocket during covid-19 lockdown, 5.1% of the total respondents are Neutral while 14.9% of the total respondents agreed with the notion. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that kidnapping 'skyrocket during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 5 also reveals that 31.4% of the total respondents disagreed that some individuals engaged in Advance fee fraud via online platforms using Covid-19 palliative as bait, 4.1% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 64.5% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that Advance fee fraud via online platforms using Covid-19 palliative as bait was common during covid-19 lockdown,

Table 2 also indicates that 40.1% of the total respondents disagreed that cybercrime increased during the pandemic, 14.4% of the total respondents are Neutral while 45.5% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that cybercrime common during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 2 also shows that 77.8% of the total respondents disagreed that pick pocketing and purse snatching increased during covid-19 lockdown, 4.1% of the total respondents are Neutral while 18.2% of the total respondents agreed with the notion. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagree that pick-pocketing and purse snatching increased during covid-19 lockdown in Idah.

Table 2 further indicate that 36.3% of the total respondents disagreed that domestic violence, such as assault within the family was major occurrence during the pandemic, 5.1% of the total respondents are Neutral while 58.5% of the total respondents agreed that domestic violence, such as assault within the family was major occurrence during the pandemic. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that domestic violence, such as assault within the family was major occurrence during covid-19 lockdown.

The distribution from the sample in table 2 also indicate that 81.3% of the total respondents disagreed that assault outside domestic spheres was common during covid-19 lockdown, 4.6% of the total respondents are Neutral while 14.1% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that assault outside domestic spheres was prevalent during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 2 equally revealed that 93.5% of the total respondents disagreed that murder resulting from cultist violent was a major occurrence during covid-19 lockdown, 1.6% of the total respondents are Neutral while 4.9% of the total respondents agreed that murder resulting from cultist violent was a major occurrence during lockdown covid-19. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that murder resulting from cultist violent was a major occurrence during covid-19 lockdown.

By and large, the information obtained from the interview conducted was in line with the findings on the types of crime that were prevalent in Idah during covid-19 lockdown in table 8; where all the interviewees affirmed that Burglary of shops, Domestic Violence, Advance Fee Fraud and Cyber Crime were the common types of crime in Idah during the covid-19 lockdown.

Table 3: Determinants of Crime during Covid-19 Lockdown in Idah.

S/N	ITEMS	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	N=369	(%)
1	Preventive measure using lockdown.	124 (33.6)	68 (18.4)	177 (48.0)	369	(100)
2	Retrenchment of workers in the private sectors due to covid-19 lockdown.	112 (30.4)	18 (4.9)	239 (64.8)	369	(100)
3	Economic hardship/poverty	47 (12.7)	22 (6.0)	300 (81.3)	369	(100)
4	Increase in internet usage for online transactions as well as working from in-office to online modification.	103 (27.9)	49 (13.3)	217 (58.8)	369	(100)
5	Government poor planning to cushion the effect of Covid-19 lockdown.	84 (22.8)	24 (6.5)	261 (70.7)	369	(100)
6	Inadequate palliative.	88 (23.8)	9 (2.4)	272 (73.7)	369	(100)
7	The escalation in social tension and family pressure.	121 (32.8)	40 (10.8)	208 (56.4)	369	(100)

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The distribution from the sample in table 3 shows that 33.6% of the total respondents disagreed that preventive measures during lockdown determine crimes, 18.4% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 48% of the total respondents agreed that preventive measures using lockdown, determined crime. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that preventive measures during lockdown was a determinant of crime.

Table 3 further revealed that 30.4% of the total respondents disagree that retrenchment of workers in the private sectors due to covid-19 lockdown was the determinants of crime, 4.9% of the total respondents are Neutral while 64.8% of the total respondents agreed that retrenchment of workers in the private sectors due to covid-19 lockdown was a determinant of crime; This shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that retrenchment of workers in the private sectors due to covid-19 lockdown were determinant of crime.

Table 3 also indicate that 12.7% of the total respondents disagreed that economic hardship/poverty was majorly caused determine crime during covid-19 lockdown, 6% of the total respondents are Neutral while 81.3% of the total respondents agreed that economic hardship/poverty were determinant

of crime. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that economic hardship/poverty was majorly determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 3 also illustrate that 27.9% of the total respondents disagreed that increase in internet usage for online transactions as well as working from office to online modification was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown, 13.3% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 58.8% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that Increase in internet usage for online transactions as well as working from in office to online modification was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown.

It was further revealed from the sample in table 3 that 22.8% of the total respondents disagreed that Government poor planning to cushion the determine crime during covid-19 lockdown, 6.5% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 70.7% of the total respondents agreed notion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that Government poor planning to cushion was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown.

The distribution in table 3 also indicates that 23.8% of the total respondents disagreed that inadequate palliative was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown, 2.4% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 73.7% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that inadequate palliative increase the impact of the pandemic on the citizen.

Table 3 further shows that 32.8% of the total respondents disagreed that there is escalation in social tension and family pressure, was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown during covid-19 lockdown, 10.8% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 56.4% of the total respondents agreed that escalation in social tension and family pressure, was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that escalation in social tension and family pressure, was a determinant of crime during covid-19 lockdown.

However, information obtained from the interview conducted indicate that nine men out of twelve representing Majority of the interviewee stated that hardship arising from covid-19 and poverty were the major determinant of crime in Idah during Covid-19 lockdown.

Table 4: Influence of Covi-19 Lockdown on Crime Rate in Idah.

S/N	ITEMS	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	N=369	(%)
1	The rate of crime occurrence was high prior to Covid-19 lockdown.	135 (36.6)	50 (13.6)	184 (49.9)	369	(100)
2	Covid-19 lockdown era had significantly influenced rise in crime rate.	141 (38.2)	28 (7.6)	200 (54.2)	369	(100)
3	The rate of crime occurrence increase after Covid-19 lockdown	174 (47.2)	41 (11.1)	154 (41.7)	369	(100)
4	Crime rate during covid-19 lockdown was measured as a result of been a victim of crime.	354 (95.9)	-	15 (4.1)	369	(100)

5	Crime rate during covid-19 lockdown was estimated base on information heard on crime incidence	55 (14.9)	8 (2.2)	306 (82.9)	369	(100)
6	Crime reported to the law enforcement agency during covid-19 lockdown does not align with the actual crime committed	6 (1.6)	203(55.0)	160 (43.4)	S369	(100)

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4 provide the distribution of the influence of covid-19 lockdown on crime rate in Idah from the sample which indicate that 36.6% of the total respondents disagreed that the rate of crime occurrence were high prior to covid-19 lockdown, 13.6% of the total respondents are Neutral while 49.9% of the total respondents agreed that the rate of crime occurrence were high prior to covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the respondents agreed that the rate of crime occurrence were high prior to covid-19 lockdown.

Table 4 further shows that 38.2% of the total respondents disagreed that Covid-19 lockdown era had significantly influenced rise in crime rate, 7.6% of the total respondents are Neutral while 54.2% of the total respondents agreed that Covid-19 lockdown era had significantly influenced rise in crime rate. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that Covid-19 lockdown era had significantly influenced rise in crime rate. This is assumption was in agreement with the information obtained from the interview conducted, which stated that majority of the interviewee representing Eight out of Twelve men of Nigerian Police in Idah division estimated that the influenced of Covid-19 Lockdown on crime rates in Idah was high; which implies that crime rate was high in the era of covid-19 lockdown.

Table 4 also indicate that 47.2% of the total respondents disagreed that the rate of crime occurrence increases after covid-19 lockdown, 11.1% of the total respondents are Neutral while 41.7% of the total respondents agreed that the rate of crime occurrence increase after covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that the rate of crime occurrence increase after covid-19 lockdown.

The distribution from the sample in table 4 also indicate that 95.9% of the total respondents disagreed that crime rate measurement was a result of been a victim of crime, while 4.1% of the total respondents agreed. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that crime rate measurement was a result of been a victim.

Table 4 also revealed that 14.9% of the total respondents disagree that crime rate were estimated base on numerous information heard on crime incidence, 2.2% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 82.9% of the total respondents agreed that crime rate were estimated base on numerous information heard on crime incidence. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that crime rate were estimated base on numerous information heard on crime incidence.

Table 4 also indicate that 1.6% of the total respondents disagreed that crime reported to the law enforcement agency does not align with the actual crime committed, 55% of the total respondents are Neutral while 43.4% of the total respondents agreed that crime reported to the law enforcement agency does not align with the actual crime committed. These shows that majority of the total

respondents are Neutral that crime reported to the law enforcement agency does not align with the actual crime committed.

Table 5: Effect of Crime on Residents of Idah during Covid-19 Lockdown.

S/N	ITEMS	DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	AGREE	N=369	(%)
1	Crime during Covid-19 lockdown had an effect on the residents of Idah.	84 (22.8)	12 (3.3)	273 (74.0)	369	(100)
2	It erodes the sense of safety of the residents.	218 (59.1)	23 (6.2)	128 (34.7)	369	(100)
3	Increase in fear / anxiety among the residents.	97 (26.3)	17 (4.6)	255 (69.1)	369	(100)
4	Increase in poverty.	26 (7.0)	-	343 (93.0)	369	(100)
5	Declined in socio-economic activities of the residents.	14 (3.8)	20 (5.4)	335 (90.8)	369	(100)
6	Folding-up of businesses.	52 (14.1)	38 (10.3)	279 (75.6)	369	(100)
7	Crime during Covid-19 lockdown led to worsen hunger among residents.	33 (8.9)	109 (29.5)	227 (61.5)	369	(100)
8	Rise in property loses.	47 (12.7)	105 (28.5)	217 (58.8)	369	(100)
9	It led to loses of lives among residents.	211 (57.2)	63 (17.1)	95 (25.7)	369	(100)

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 5 above shows that 22.8% of the total respondents disagreed that crime during covid-19 lockdown had an effects on the residents of Idah, 3.3% of the total respondents are Neutral while 74% of the total respondents agreed that crime during covid-19 lockdown had an effects on the residents of Idah. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that crime during covid-19 lockdown had an effects on the residents of Idah.

Table 5 also shows that 59.1% of the total respondents disagreed that crime during covid-19 lockdowns erode the sense of safety of the residents, 6.2% of the total respondents are Neutral while 34.7% of the total respondents agreed that crime during covid-19 lockdowns erode the sense of safety of the residents. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that covid-19 erode the sense of safety of the residents.

Table 5 also revealed that 26.3% of the total respondents disagreed that increase in fear / anxiety among the residents was caused by the pandemic, 4.6% of the total respondents are Neutral while 69.1% of the total respondents agreed that increase in fear / anxiety among the residents was caused by the pandemic. This shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that increase in fear / anxiety among the residents was caused by the pandemic.

Table 5 also indicates that, 7% of the total respondents disagreed that increase in poverty was the effects of crime during covid-19 lockdown, while 93% of the total respondents agreed that increase in poverty was the effects of crime during covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that increase in poverty was the effects of crime during covid-19 lockdown: this is in agreement with the information obtained from the interview conducted which stated the majority of the interviewee representing Seven out of Twelve men of Nigerian Police in Idah division assumed that increase in poverty was the major effect of crime in Idah during covid-19 lockdown.

It was also revealed that 3.8% of the total respondents disagreed that declined in socio-economic capacity of the residents was an effect of crime on residents during covid-19 lockdown, 5.4% of the total respondents are Neutral while 90.8% of the total respondents agreed with the notion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that declined in socio-economic activities of the residents was an effect of crime on residents during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 5 also indicates that 14.1% of the total respondents disagreed that Folding-up of businesses was a resultant effect of crime on residents during covid-19 lockdown, 10.3% of the total respondents were Neutral, while 75.6% of the total respondents agreed with the assertion. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that Folding-up of businesses was a resultant effects of crime during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 5 also shows that 8.9% of the total respondents disagreed that Crime during Covid-19 lockdown led to worsen hunger among residents, 29.5% of the total respondents are Neutral while 61.5% of the total respondents agreed Crime during Covid-19 lockdown led to worsen hunger among residents. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that Crime during Covid-19 lockdown led to worsen hunger among residents.

Table 5 further revealed that 12.7% of the total respondents disagreed that property losses was an effect of crime during covid-19 lockdown, 28.5% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 58.8% of the total respondents agreed that crime during covid-19 lockdown led to rise in property losses. These shows that majority of the total respondents agreed that increase in property losses were the effect of crime during covid-19 lockdown.

Table 5 also indicates that 57.2% of the total respondents disagreed that there was loses of lives among residents as a result of crime during the lockdown, 17.1% of the total respondents are Neutral, while 25.7% of the total respondents agreed that there was loses of lives among residents as due to crime effect during Covid-19 lockdown. These shows that majority of the total respondents disagreed that there was loses of lives among residents as a result of crime during the lockdown.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis- Model Summaries

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.981 ^a	.963	.962	.12498

a. Predictors: (Constant) TCDCL, DCDCLI, ICLCR, ECRCL

The R-square value of .981 in table 6 indicated that the components of independent variable have a combined effect of 98.1% on the dependent variable while the adjusted R-square value of .962 also indicated the accurate influence of the combined effect of the independent variables and the dependent variable of 96.2% on crime in Idah, Idah Local Government Area, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	146.411	4	36.603	2343.191	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.686	364	.016		
	Total	152.097	368			

a. Dependent Variable: CL
 b. Predictors: (Constant)TCPDCL, DCDCLI, ICLCRI , ECRIDCL

TCPDCL: Types of Crime Prevalence During Covid-19 Lockdown in Idah

DCDCLI: Determinant of Crime During Covid-19 Lockdown in Idah

ICLCR; Influence of Covid-19 Lockdown on Crime Rates in Idah

ECRIDCL: Effect of Crime on Residents of Idah During Covid-19 Lockdown

The F-Statistics value of 2343.191 and the significant level of .000 in table 7 signified that the model is fit and significant at 5% level. This means that the result is good and admissible for decision making.

Table 8: Regression Coefficients

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.116	.035		-3.275	.001
	TCDCL	.146	.027	.130	5.445	.000
	DCDCLI	.073	.027	.091	2.720	.007
	ICLCR	.380	.030	.367	12.648	.000
	ECRDCL	.486	.034	.434	14.209	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CL

Test of Hypotheses

To analyze the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, Idah Local Government Area, Kogi State, Nigeria, the formulated hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression Analysis.

Hypothesis 1: The types of crime prevalent in Idah has no significant relationship with the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah

Furthermore, table 8 shows that the result of t-statistic value of 5.445 and the corresponding sig. level of .000 which is significant at 5% level of significance indicating that the types of crime prevalent in Idah have no significant relationship with the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah. Based on this, the null hypothesis one which states that the types of crime prevalent in Idah have no significant relationship with the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, is rejected while the alternate hypothesis which states that the types of crime prevalent in Idah have significant relationship with the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Covid-19 lockdown and the determinant of crime in Idah.

Also, table 8 shows that the result of t-statistic value of 2.720 and the corresponding sig. level of .007 which is significant at 5% level of significance indicating that there is significant relationship between

the influence of Covid-19 lockdown and the determinant of crime in Idah. Based on this, the null hypothesis two, which states that there is no significant relationship between the influence of Covid-19 lockdown and the determinant of crime in Idah is rejected while the alternate hypothesis which states that there is significant relationship between the influence of Covid-19 lockdown and the determinant of crime in Idah is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: The influence of Covid-19 lockdown has no significant relationship with crime rate in Idah.

Table 8 shows that the result of t-statistic value of 12.648 and the corresponding sig. level of .000 which is significant at 5% level of significance indicating that Covid-19 lockdown has positive and significant influence on crime rate in Idah. Based on this, the null hypothesis three which states that influence of Covid-19 lockdown has no significant relationship with crime rate in Idah is rejected while the alternate hypothesis which states that Covid-19 lockdown has positive and significant influence on crime rate in Idah is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: Influence of Covid-19 lockdown has no significant effect of crime on residents of Idah.

More so, table 8 shows that the result of t-statistic value of 14.209 and the corresponding sig. level of .000 which is significant at 5% level of significance indicating that influence of Covid-19 lockdown has significant effect of crime on residents of Idah. Based on this, the null hypothesis four which states that influence of Covid-19 lockdown has no significant effect on crime on residents of Idah is rejected while the alternate hypothesis which states that influence of Covid-19 lockdown has significant effect of crime on residents of Idah is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

This study revealed that the types of crime prevalent in Idah has significant relationship with the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, indicating that a unit increase in the type of crime prevalent in Idah would lead to an increase in the influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah. The emergence of Covid-19 brought about so many prevalent types of crime in Idah which affected the security of the people of Idah. This finding is in line with the findings of Abrams (2020), Ekpenyong *et al* (2020), as well as finding from interview conducted with the Nigerian police in Idah (2023) which found that Covid19 lockdown caused a rise in certain crime types, such as burglary, armed robbery, cybercrime, domestic violence, and gender-based violence. Although, all these crime were homogeneously found trending in this study except robbery. While there was a disagreement in findings of Halford *et at* (2020), Cheung and Gunby (2022), which found that there is an overall decrease in crime types during covid-19 lockdown.

This study also revealed that there is significant relationship between the influence of Covid-19 lockdown and the determinant of crime in Idah, indicating that a unit increase in influence of Covid-19 lockdown, it would lead to an increase in determinant of crime in Idah. There are many determinant of crime that may likely to arise if there is persistent lockdown. This finding in agreement with the findings of Abdullahi *et al.*(2021) and Akanmu *et al.* (2021), as well as the information obtained from the interview conducted, which reveals that crime during covid-19 lockdown were attributed to analytical agents such as poverty, idleness and poor governance, as well as shutting down of economy: Although, the researcher have not found disagreement with the findings of this study on the determinants of crimes during covid-19 lockdown.

This study revealed that Covid-19 lockdown have positive and significant influence on crime rate in Idah, indicating that a unit increase in Covid-19 lockdown would lead to an increase in crime rate in Idah. The lockdown if allow to persist would lead to increase in crime rate in Idah because once people are idol and don' t have what to eat, they are most likely to engage in crime. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Abdullahi *et al* (2021) Akanmu *et al.* (2021), Ekpenyong *et al*, (2020); which found that there was an upsurge in crime rate during covid-19 lockdown. While the finding of

UNODC (2020), disagreement with the above finding, which stated that, there is global 50% decline in crime rate, especially in country with stringent lockdown policies.

Lastly, the study revealed that influence of Covid-19 lockdown has significant effect of crime on residents of Idah, indicating that a unit increase in influence of Covid-19 lockdown would lead to an increase in crime effects on residents of Idah. The advent of the pandemic and the lockdown of most business places lead to increase in crime effect on residents of Idah. This finding was homogeneous with the information obtained from the interview conducted on Influence of Covid-19 lockdown on crime in Idah, but the findings was heterogeneous with the findings of Poblete-Cazaneva (2020), which stated that large negative effects were observed for divers' types of crimes such as murder (61%), theft (63%), and crime against women (64%).

Conclusion

Covid-19 is a very disturbing global reality that led many government of the world to implement lockdown measure in other to limit human to human transmission of the corona virus. Besides, the lockdown as a preventive measure did not prevent crime from occurring. However, the types of crimes that were prevalent during Covid-19 lockdown in Idah were: burglary of the commercial areas resulting from absenteeism affecting lack of guardianship, advance free fraud, domestic violence (assault within the family) due to locking down of the victims with their predators and growing cybercrime due to the routine activity of the internet users which exposed them to cybercriminal. Besides, there was reduction in the following types of crime: burglary of residential areas due to home presence and guardianship; assault outside domestic spheres, murder arising from cultist violent crime, pick pocketing and purse snatching due to movement restriction, closures of bar, restaurants and night clubbing.

Though, the major determinants of crime during covid-19 lockdown was economic hardship/ poverty due to closure of business and sources of livelihood, inadequate palliative and government poor planning to cushion the effect of covid-19. Whereas, the study reveals that covid-19 lockdown had influence rise in crime rate in Idah.

More so, the study shows that, crime during covid-19 lockdown have had significant effects on the residents of Idah, it was also found that there was increase in poverty, decline in socioeconomic capacity, increase in the number of victims of counterfeit and illicit product as well as fake medical product/ personal protective equipment.

Recommendations

Base on the findings that emanated from this study and the conclusion reached, the researcher makes the following recommendations which are capable of reducing crime rate during any likely pandemic lockdown in Nigeria and Idah Local Government in particular;

1. The study recommends for Idah government authority to install an electronic surveillance as an apparatus that could aids detection of different kinds of crimes at all time, as this could be helpful during an emergency period such as COVID-19 lockdown era.
2. The Nigerian government nee to provide sufficient palliative with widely and fairly distribution to cushion the effect of any likely pandemic lockdown, as this will help in reducing the level at which economic hardship/ poverty could push some individual into crime in an emergency period like this.
3. The study also recommends for Idah Local Government Authority to empower community Policing to have a vehicular patrol team to aids Nigeria police in crime detection, as this could be helpful in reducing crime rates during any emergency like covid-19 lockdown.
4. The study also suggests that government should always include in her budget a poverty alleviation fund for an emergency period like COVID-19 and its subsequent lockdown, to avert the level at which increase in poverty resulting from pandemic lockdown hardship could push people into crime.

Conflict of Interests

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Authors' contributions

Alidu Yakubu Musa carried out the research work.

Edime Yunusa reviewed the manuscript and analysed parts of the data

Thomas Imoudu Gomment supervised the research work.

All authors proofread and approved the final manuscript.

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